

1 **Therapeutic targeting in breast cancer for the treatment of lymph node metastasis: NBPF20.**

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6 Metastasis is the major cause of death from cancer (1); metastasis to the lymph nodes in breast cancer is
7 dangerous, relatively common, and in one study ranged from 10-60% based on molecular subtype (2-4).
8 We predict therapeutic index is intrinsically linked to differential expression which can be comprehensively
9 and blindly determined using whole transcriptome data (5). We pioneered understanding of metastasis to
10 the lymph nodes as an intermediate biological and anatomical counterpart to the CNS metastasis in
11 humans (6-12). Here we utilize whole transcriptome technologies (13, 14) to measure total transcription in
12 the lymph node metastases and primary tumors of humans with breast cancer for discovery and insight
13 into clonal evolution through disease progression. We identify here a therapeutic target based on its
14 differential expression and up-regulation upon metastasis to the lymph nodes in humans with breast
15 cancer, NBPF20, as a candidate therapeutic target for the medical management of lymph node
16 metastasis.
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We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the lymph nodes to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the lymph node metastatic transcriptome in breast cancer: a therapeutic target that is up-regulated and metastasis-specific, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy: NBPF20.

Results

Figure 1: NBPF20 is differentially expressed in lymph node metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

I. Lymph node metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

n=18 primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

n=16 lymph node metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
201103_x_at	1.25E-01	-1.5730534	-4.96012	-0.23850516	NBPF20	2835/22277	87.3

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the breast and in lymph node metastases of humans with breast cancer (13), we discovered differential expression of neuroblastoma breakpoint family member 20, encoded by *NBPF20* in metastasis to the lymph nodes in humans with breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of NBPF20 changed more than 85% of the human lymph node metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,277 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of NBPF20 messenger RNA in lymph node metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of NBPF20 during disease progression and dissemination in breast cancer.

II. Lymph node metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

n=36 primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

n=36 lymph node metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
213612_x_at	2.33E-01	-1.2035	-5.32181	-0.1200461	NBPF20	6889/22277	69.1

Through measurement of total transcription in the lymph node metastases of humans with breast cancer as compared to primary tumors of the breast, we validated differential expression of NBPF20 in metastasis to the lymph node in breast cancer (**Chart 2**) (14). The expression of NBPF20 here changed more than nearly 70% of the lymph node metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,277 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of NBPF20 messenger RNA in lymph node metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of NBPF20 during disease progression and dissemination in humans with breast cancer.

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2 Thus, differential and increased expression of NBPF20 defines the lymph node metastatic
3 transcriptome in human breast cancer.

4 **Discussion**

5 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
6 treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like
7 trastuzumab). Inhibitors of NBPF20, immunoglobulin or small molecule based (once evaluated for toxicity
8 and safety) can immediately be tested for efficacy in patients with lymph node metastasis who have failed
9 previous treatment, with the ultimate goal of identifying the most effective inhibitors of lymph node
10 metastasis in humans with breast cancer who have not yet progressed but are at predicted high risk, or
11 those whose metastasis has not yet become unmanageable due to metastasis size, number or location. A
12 multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis,
13 replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, targeting *CDKN* inactivation and
14 ATP-binding cassette pump expression in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective in limiting
15 tumor clone resistance (15).
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Methods

We utilized GSE44408 (13) for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the lymph nodes and in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer (along with GSE57968 [14] for target validation) using microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods.